

An Investigation of the Influences of Classroom Intervention Strategies on the Autonomy and Motivation of Adolescent Language Learners in Foreign Language Acquisition Contexts

-A Pilot Experimental Research Project

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Abstract

This pilot study examined the influences of two classroom intervention strategies on the autonomy and motivation of adolescent language learners in the context of the acquisition of Spanish as a foreign language. It involved a 5-week quasi-experiment and used different methodological approaches with the intention of producing answers to the following two research questions: Do the intervention strategies influence learner motivation and, if so, how? Do the intervention strategies influence learner autonomy and, if so, how?

The student sample consisted of 29 females, aged 15 to 17 years, from a secondary school in Ireland; the experiment comprised a treatment (13 students) and comparison (16 students) group. Although the teacher-participant used the intervention strategies to teach the treatment group, she did not depart from her traditional approach with the comparison group. The most important results were the increased levels of both learner autonomy and motivation.

1. Introduction

Over the past four decades, learner autonomy and motivation have become two focal points of L2 (target language) research, emerging as equally significant factors affecting L2 acquisition. Extensively studied as individual concepts, links have been made between autonomy and motivation since the 1980s [1]. This study examined the influences of two intervention strategies (content negotiation and promotion of self-evaluation) on both learner autonomy and motivation.

To begin, the research content and rationale are explained, followed by a description of the participants and then, the design and methodology.

Finally, the results, discussion, conclusion and pedagogical implications sections are presented.

2. Research Rationale

Autonomy and motivation have equally received a great deal of attention in L2 research, yet the essence of such research has not focused on how both concepts are affected following the introduction of ISs (intervention strategies). While decreasing levels of engagement are especially associated with secondary education [2, 3], many of the existing studies concentrate on tertiary education, with young adults usually the focus of the research [4, 5, 6]. What is more, decreasing levels of motivation are particularly problematic in language classrooms [7, 8], thus there appears to be a need to generate motivation in second-level language classrooms.

While longitudinal studies have been conducted to investigate autonomy and motivation [4, 9], the majority are cross-sectional in design. Furthermore, much of the existing research has not focused on FLA (foreign language acquisition) contexts where motivation is regarded as more crucial than SLA (second language acquisition) contexts, as the former rarely allows for opportunities to communicate in the L2 outside of the classroom [2].

Given the great difficulty in detecting such reports, there appears a need for comprehensive studies of the effect(s) of ISs on *both* autonomy and motivation, which the present study has investigated.

3. The research participants

The school, which partook in this study, is an all girls' secondary level institute in the west of Ireland. The student-participants were chosen from TY (Transition Year), as they had prior knowledge of the

L2 and, more importantly, were not preparing for state examinations.

As shown in Table 1, the student sample consisted of a treatment and comparison group, ranging in age from 15 to 17 years. A background questionnaire was designed to verify that the groups were similar enough to compare in terms of demographics and how long they had been studying Spanish. Unpaired t-tests were carried out and indicated that the groups did not differ significantly on any of the background characteristics.

Table 1. Student-participant groups

Treatment Group n = 13, age μ = 15.85	Comparison Group n = 16, age μ = 15.94
Alicia	Adriana
Gabriela	Alba
Imelda	Ana
Juana	Antonia
Leticia	Blanca
Maria	Camila
Olivia	Carla
Pepa	Cristina
Paca	Elena
Roberta	Esperanza
Salma	Luisa
Tatiana	Pilar
Tessa	Ramona
	Rosa
	Silvia
	Sofia

The groups were of mixed ability and both attended three 35-minute Spanish lessons per week. One teacher was recruited; she was the teacher of both the treatment and comparison group prior to and during the research project.

4. Research design and methodology

The design and methodology section is divided into two parts: the quasi-experimental procedure; and the research instruments.

4.1. Quasi-experimental procedure

Quasi-experiments often contain causal research elements to gather evidence regarding cause-and-effect relationships. In this case, the cause variable was the ISs, while the effect variables were learner motivation and autonomy. Both the treatment and comparison groups followed the same syllabus for Spanish (as determined by the school and the Irish *Department of Education and Science*), the difference

being that the treatment group was taught with the aid of the two ISs.

Table 2. Intervention Strategies

Intervention Strategies	Objectives
Content negotiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners have greater freedom in choosing learning materials and methods • Greater allowances made for individual styles of learning • Classroom focus shifts from teaching to learning and from teacher to learner • Learners develop greater ownership of their learning
Promotion of Self-evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners develop self-evaluation skills • Existing motivation maintained and rewarded

As shown in Table 2, the first IS, content negotiation, involved giving students choice in learning materials. The learning aims listed in the their textbook were the basis on which they chose materials, with the teacher on hand to facilitate and advise. When individuals had chosen their materials, they pooled them together in groups of three or four and planned how to use their resources with the teacher's support. The groups remained together for the duration of the study and the teacher assisted them day-to-day by making her knowledge available.

The second IS, the promotion of self-evaluation, was employed to generate and maintain motivation. Each student stated three personal learning goals and plans to achieve those goals. They reviewed their progress, commenting on why they thought they were or were not achieving their goals.

While only the treatment group received the IS-treatment, both groups completed questionnaires and some members from each group were interviewed. Both groups were observed to ensure that the ISs were correctly implemented with the treatment group and that effect variables (autonomy and motivation) were controlled with the comparison group.

4.3. Research Instruments

The instruments included motivation and autonomy questionnaires, reflection records, and goal-setting and evaluation records. The students were assigned aliases for labelling research data.

Adapted from the AMTB [10] and Deci and Ryan's motivational scales [1], both groups completed a pre- and post- motivation questionnaire to investigate their motivational types (instrumental

or intrinsic) and levels (high/moderate/low) towards the L2.

Both groups also completed a pre- and post-autonomy questionnaire to investigate their levels of autonomy towards the L2. The questionnaire was adapted from those developed by Spratt, Humphreys and Chan [11], and Gallacher [12].

The treatment group completed the reflection record fortnightly, adapted from the record of work used in the *University of Hong Kong* [13, p.158].

The treatment group also completed the goal-setting and evaluation record based on that developed by *Iowa State University*. They stated three personal learning goals, followed by a review of their progress and then, a reflection on why they achieved or did not achieve their goals. Finally, the teacher provided learners with feedback.

5. Results

The results section is presented in five parts: the motivation questionnaire; the autonomy questionnaire; the goal-setting and evaluation record; the reflection record; and interviews.

5.1. Motivation questionnaire

The difference between the pre- and post- mean scores for the treatment group's intrinsic motivation ($\mu_d = 0.10$) was not significantly higher than the corresponding score for the comparison group ($\mu_d = 0.03$). A two-sample t-test found that Critical- $t_{27} = 2.14$ and calc- $t = -1.21$ for intrinsic motivation, therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis. Similarly, with Critical- $t_{27} = 2.18$ and calc- $t = 1$ for instrumental motivation, we again fail to reject the null hypothesis; therefore these were not statistically significant findings. However, intrinsically motivated students were revealed to have higher levels of motivation, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Intrinsic motivation vs. motivational levels (n = 29)

The pre- treatment results from the full sample ($n = 29$) showed that 50% of the intrinsically motivated students had high-level motivation, while 0% of the instrumentally motivated students had high-level motivation. In fact, 54.5% of the instrumentally motivated students actually had low-level motivation.

Moving on to motivational levels, Table 3 shows the intergroup comparison. The difference between the pre- and post- mean scores for the treatment group's motivation ($\mu_d = 1.76$) was significantly higher than the corresponding score for the comparison group ($\mu_d = -0.13$).

Table 3. Intergroup comparison of means for motivational levels (n = 29)

	Treatment (n = 13)	Comparison (n = 16)
Mean difference	1.76	-0.13
Independent t-tests		
t calc	3.22	
t critical	2.14	
p value	0.01	

Independent t-tests: $df = 27$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$

The two-sample t-test found that Critical- t_{27} (2.14) was less than calc- t (3.22) and $p = 0.01$; thus we reject the null hypothesis, as there was a significant increase in the treatment group's motivational levels.

5.2. Autonomy questionnaire

As presented in Table 4, the difference between the pre- and post- mean scores for the treatment group's autonomy levels ($\mu_d = 0.46$) was significantly higher than the corresponding score for the comparison group ($\mu_d = -0.06$).

Table 4. Intergroup comparisons of means for autonomy levels (n = 29)

	Treatment (n = 13)	Comparison (n = 16)
Mean difference	0.46	-0.06
Independent t-tests		
t calc	3.34	
t critical	2.12	
p value	0.00	

Independent t-tests: $df = 27$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$

The independent t-test found that Critical- t_{27} (2.14) was less than calc- t (3.22) and $p = 0.01$, therefore we reject the null hypothesis. Hence these were statistically significant findings.

5.3. Goal-setting and evaluation record

In analysing the goal-setting and evaluation record, the researcher looked for evidence that the treatment group had been planning and evaluating learning. Suitable written comments were placed under the categories of “planning learning” and “evaluating learning” where appropriate.

Almost 85% of the group reported achieving their goals. Paca and Tessa had not achieved one of their goals during the first self-evaluation, however, both realised their goals by the final evaluation. Gabriela and Tatiana, whose autonomy and motivational levels remained low, reported not achieving their goals by the final evaluation.

5.4. Reflection record

In order to analyse the students’ reflections with regard to autonomy, the researcher looked for comments that indicated learners had been accepting responsibility, planning tasks, executing tasks, taking initiative and taking risks (in terms of striving to speak Spanish as much as possible). All of the identified comments were from students whose autonomy levels had increased. Their comments suggested they had become more autonomous as a result of the learning environment produced by ISs; for example Paca stated “We’re really trying to chat in Spanish...we never used to do that before”. This comment indicated that there had been a change towards more autonomous behaviour with students striving to communicate in Spanish.

In terms of motivation, the researcher looked for comments indicating that learners had shown positive task orientation, enthusiasm, need for achievement, high aspirations, goal orientation and perseverance. The identified comments indicated that motivation levels increased as a direct result of the treatment. Pepa stated “I actually don’t mind going to Spanish class these days, even think it’s a bit of fun”; this comment suggested that she had become more enthused about attending Spanish lessons and her motivation results moved from the low- to the moderate-level category. Before the treatment commenced Pepa had named Spanish as her third least preferred subject.

5.5 Interviews

While five students from each group were to be interviewed, regrettably only two students from the comparison and one from the treatment group partook. The students were each asked the following

two questions: 1) What are your views on students taking greater responsibility of their own Spanish learning, in terms of choosing learning materials, planning lessons, setting learning goals and self-evaluating?; and 2) What are your thoughts on the teacher’s role in this scenario where she would be there to advise, guide, monitor and encourage students? The treatment group student was asked to reflect and share her thoughts having experienced such a learning environment, while the comparison group students simply offered their opinions and thoughts on introducing the approach hypothetically.

The treatment group participant, Imelda, was categorised as moderately autonomous in both the pre- and post- results, although her level increased by 7%. Her motivation moved from the low to the moderate category, with a 13% increase. Imelda spoke positively about her experience asserting the positive influence caused by gaining greater freedom in choosing learning materials and planning lessons, as well as the new role of the teacher. She suggested that having greater control over learning and the subsequent improvement in her own learning were both highly motivating factors.

Luisa and Sofia of the comparison group were also interviewed. Luisa’s results showed that she had a high level of motivation and a moderate level of autonomy, while Sofia displayed low levels of both. While these students did not receive the treatment, they too spoke positively about gaining greater control over learning, as well as the subsequent changes in teachers’ responsibilities.

6. Discussion

Similar to the findings of previous studies [14], a strong positive correlation was found between intrinsic type and high-level motivation. This was in keeping with Ely’s study [15], which found that knowledge of learners’ motivational types predicted their levels. While the comparison group’s motivational types did not change, there was a minor increase in the treatment group’s intrinsic type. Despite this, t-tests indicated that the ISs had not influenced motivational types.

Some believe that motivational level or strength is not fixed [2]; before the experiment commenced, the number of treatment group participants with low-level motivation outnumbered those with high-level. However, post- treatment results indicated that there had been an increase in motivation with the number of students showing high levels exceeding that of those with low levels. The comparison group’s pre- and post- mean scores did not differ significantly. The results of the t-tests suggested that the ISs had positively influenced learner motivation by

increasing overall levels. Similarly, previous studies [2, 16] also reported increased motivation following the introduction of classroom ISs.

While the treatment group did not show high levels of autonomy either before or after the treatment, their overall level increased. In contrast, the comparison group's pre- and post- autonomy did not differ significantly. The t-tests suggested that the ISs had positively influenced autonomy by increasing overall levels. Similar to this, Sanprasert [9] also reported that autonomy increased following the use of ISs.

The treatment group completed goal-setting and evaluation records, as well as reflection records. Approximately 85% of the group reported achieving their goals, with two students not achieving their goals. The data suggested that most students became more autonomous and reflective learners, and that planning, monitoring and evaluating their learning helped them to achieve their goals. In terms of autonomy, reflective comments indicated that learners had accepted responsibility, planned tasks, executed tasks, taken initiative and striven to speak Spanish as much as possible. In terms of motivation, the comments indicated that students had shown positive task orientation, enthusiasm, need for achievement, high aspirations, goal orientation and perseverance. The comments indicated that autonomy and motivation improved as a result of the treatment.

One treatment group student and two comparison group participants were interviewed about their views on learners and teachers' roles in classrooms that support autonomy. They spoke positively about the prospect of introducing greater autonomy and about the non-traditional role of teachers associated with its introduction. Just as Brown [17] suggests, the interviews and reflections revealed that the students felt that they could become more motivated and independent learners in a non-traditional secondary school setting that offered them greater control over the content learned, encouraged self-evaluation and where the teacher would take on a consultative role.

Noels [19] has suggested that classrooms, which facilitate autonomy, allow teachers to become less controlling, leading to improved motivation among learners. The interview data and written reflective comments revealed that treatment group began viewing the teacher's role more positively and that the teacher-student relationship improved with a greater feeling of trust between them. With the exception of one student who did not like the change in the teacher's role and another who said she would like more input from the teacher, the enhanced motivation was frequently attributed as owing to the shift in the teacher's role from a formal instructor to an advisor and facilitator.

7. Conclusion

Research question 1: Do the ISs influence learner motivation and, if so, how?

Regarding this question, the quantitative and qualitative results lean in favour of the effectiveness of the ISs in generating motivation. In contrast to the comparison group, there was a change in the treatment group's motivational levels, with a significant increase in the post- results. It might be claimed that the treatment group's increased motivation was simply a result of the students feeling they ought to feel more motivated following the introduction of a learning approach which was new to them and very different to what they were used to. Also, the researcher's presence may have influenced their responses. However, it should be mentioned that the researcher attended both groups' lessons for the purpose of observing. Another explanation for the increase in the treatment group's motivation is that the ISs resulted in a shift in the traditional teacher-student roles and relationship; this was frequently referred to as an important motivating factor by the students and has commonly been associated with enhanced motivation [17, 18].

Research question 2: Do the ISs influence learner autonomy and, if so, how?

Regarding the second question, the quantitative and qualitative results tend to confirm the effectiveness of the ISs in fostering learner autonomy. Unlike the results of the comparison group, there was an increase in the treatment group's autonomy levels. Again, it might be claimed that the increase in autonomy was merely a result of the group's awareness of being under observation and that the effects of the ISs were being measured. One explanation for the difference in the treatment group's post- autonomy levels is that the ISs involved the use of techniques that are closely associated with autonomous learning, such as setting learning goals, planning to achieve goals, self-evaluating and reflecting on the learning process. The students' interview and written responses indicated that they had taken responsibility for their learning.

8. Pedagogical implications

There are clear implications for teaching; if we want to increase students' motivation and interest in attending L2 classes in secondary school settings, we must allow them to have greater input in the learning process with teachers taking a backseat. Secondary school L2 learners have a reputation of lacking motivation [2, 3, 8, 19], thus the ISs proposed in this

study, or elements of them, should possibly be included in formal classroom settings. Many of the students' comments suggested that ISs should be implemented on a long-term basis.

Perhaps incorporating ISs into first year classes would allow teachers and students to experiment and become familiar with them, so that the ISs might be altered as appropriate and carried through to the subsequent academic years. Unlike other academic subjects taken at secondary level, the current foreign language textbooks are predetermined by the Irish *Department of Education and Science* and a required and integral part of the language syllabus across all Irish secondary schools. Owing to this, the ISs and selected materials would have to be integrated alongside current textbooks. The use of content negotiation as an IS should result in successful use of both textbooks and additional materials and methods.

It should be noted that the ISs, which were implemented in this study, are not the only or ultimate solution when it comes to fostering autonomy or tackling low levels of motivation. The researcher does not propose that teachers strictly follow the procedures that were introduced in this study, but perhaps elements of the course of action taken in this study could be introduced or these ISs could be used as a guide to introducing autonomy into language classrooms in a systematic manner.

9. References

- [1] Deci, E.L. and Ryan, R.M. (1985) *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-determination in Human Behavior*, Plenum, New York.
- [2] Guilloteaux, MJ (2007) 'Motivating Language Learners: a Classroom-oriented Investigation of Teachers' Motivational Practices and Students' Motivation', *PhD Thesis*, University of Nottingham.
- [3] Maehr, M.L. and Anderman, E.M. (1993) 'Reinventing Schools for Early Adolescents: Emphasising Task Goals', *the Elementary School Journal*, 93 (5), pp. 593-610.
- [4] Kato, F. (2009) 'Student Preferences: Goal-setting and Self-assessment Activities in a Tertiary Education Environment', *Language Teaching Research*, 13 (2), pp. 177-199.
- [5] Hongyan, W. and Hongying, G. (2006) 'Promoting Learner Autonomy for College non-English Majors through Self-assessment', *CELEA Journal*, 29(4), pp.21-27.
- [6] Wachob, P. (2006) 'Methods and Materials for Motivation and Learner Autonomy', *Reflections on English Language Teaching*, 5 (1), pp. 93-122.
- [7] Osborne, P. (2005) *Teaching English One to One: How to Teach One to One Classes for the Professional Language Teacher*, Modern English Publishing Ltd, London.
- [8] Dörnyei, Z. (2003) 'Attitudes, Orientations, and Motivations in Language Learning: Advances in Theory, Research, and Applications', in *Attitudes, Orientations, and Motivations in Language Learning* (Z. Dörnyei, Ed.). Blackwell, Oxford, pp. 3-32.
- [9] Sanprasert, N. (2010) 'The Application of a Course Management System to Enhance Autonomy in Learning English as a Foreign Language', *System*, 38 (1), pp. 109-123.
- [10] Gardner, R.C. (1985) *Social Psychology and Second Language Learning: the Role of Attitudes and Motivation*, Edward Arnold, London.
- [11] Spratt, M., Humphreys, G., Chan, V. (2002) 'Autonomy and Motivation: which Comes First?', *Language Teaching Research*, 6, pp. 245-266.
- [12] Gallacher, L. (2004) 'Learner Training with Young Learners', <http://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/think/articles/learner-training-young-learners> (2 December 2009).
- [13] Benson, P. (2001) *Teaching and Researching Autonomy in Language Learning*, Pearson Education Ltd, Harlow.
- [14] Campón, R.P. and Carrillo, E.T. (2007) 'The Motivation to Use Oral Language in the EFL Classroom in ESO and Bachillerato', *Porta Linguarum*, 7, pp. 135-151.
- [15] Ely, C.M. (1986) 'An Analysis of Discomfort, Risktaking, Sociability, and Motivation in the L2 Classroom', *Language Learning*, 36 (1), pp. 1-25.
- [16] Guilloteaux, M.J. and Dörnyei, Z. (2008) 'Motivating Language Learners: a Classroom-oriented Investigation of the Effects of Motivational Strategies on Student Motivation', *TESOL*, 42 (1), pp. 55-77.
- [17] Brown, H.D. (1994) *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*, Prentice Hall Regents, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- [18] Noels, K.A., (2001) 'Learning Spanish as a Second Language: Learners' Orientations and Perceptions of their Teachers' Communication Style', *Language Learning*, 51 (1), pp. 107-144.
- [19] Gardner, R.C. (2001) *Language Learning Motivation: the Student, the Teacher, and the Researcher*, *Foreign Language Education*; <http://studentorgs.utexas.edu/flesa/tpfle/contents1.doc> (12 July 2008).